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Archimedes Optimization-Driven CNN in Federated Settings: A Case Study on Thyroid Disease Diagnosis

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ABSTRACT

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is playing an increasingly vital role in the healthcare industry, driving the transformation toward smart systems that enhance diagnostic accuracy, enable personalized treatment, and support efficient clinical decision-making. In this context, predicting thyroid disease is critical for long-term patient management and improving survival outcomes. However, traditional machine learning approaches face limitations due to data privacy concerns and the distributed nature of healthcare data. In this study, we propose a federated learning (FL) framework for the classification of thyroid disease using convolutional neural networks (CNNs). To further improve model performance, we employ the Archimedes Optimization Algorithm (AOA) to optimize CNN parameters, ensuring efficient convergence and enhanced predictive accuracy. FL approach enables collaborative training across multiple healthcare institutions without exposing sensitive patient data, thus preserving privacy through decentralized learning. We evaluate and compare several federated learning algorithms and client trainings based on classification accuracy and f1-score. Experimental results demonstrate that the AOA-optimized CNN within the FL framework outperforms client local trainings. The accuracy rate of 90.68% obtained with the FedProx algorithm shows that it achieves performance comparable to that of the centralized learning approach.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, artificial intelligence (AI) has become an essential transformation tool in many fields, especially in the healthcare systems [1]. Its integration into hospitals and clinics is bringing about a fundamental change in medical care processes. AI is being used effectively in many clinical applications such as disease diagnosis, prediction of patient outcomes and the creation of personalized treatment plans.

Machine learning methods are among the effective analysis tools widely used in healthcare. These methods can offer higher accuracy rates compared to subjective evaluations of experts, especially in diagnostic processes. In order to develop a reliable prediction model in the healthcare sector, a large and diverse dataset is needed. In this context, inter-institutional collaborative studies make it possible to achieve more successful results than institution-based prediction systems by increasing data diversity and patient features [2].

Smart healthcare systems have traditionally relied on centralized artificial intelligence systems, especially cloud-based or data center-supported solutions for learning and analyzing health data [3]. Today, however, the significant increase in the volume of health data and the rapid proliferation of Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) devices in healthcare networks present these centralized structures with various challenges. Communication delays, especially during the transmission of raw data to the center, reduce the ability of these systems to respond in a timely manner and cause them to fall short in terms of scalability. Moreover, the direct sharing of patient data in centralized learning approaches increases the risk of privacy breaches. Given the increasing number of data breaches in healthcare organizations, protecting data security and privacy has become a key global agreed priority [4].

Federated learning is an innovative artificial intelligence method developed to overcome issues such as data privacy, security and interoperability [5]. First proposed by Google in 2017, this approach enables collaborative model training without the need for data sharing between institutions or organizations. Especially in areas with sensitive data, such as the healthcare sector, federated learning allows data to be analyzed without leaving the organization, thereby increasing model accuracy and reducing the costs that may arise as a result of potential data breaches.

Deep learning is an advanced machine learning method that enables computers and intelligent systems to make human-like logical inferences on complex data [6]. Initially developed on the basis of artificial neural networks, this approach, as a result of many years of research and technological advances, has demonstrated superior performance compared to traditional machine learning algorithms. Today, deep learning techniques are widely used in many application areas such as bioinformatics, medical image analysis, sensor data evaluation, medical information systems and public health.

CNNs are highly flexible models that can learn complex nonlinear patterns from data; however, their performance depends heavily on careful tuning of parameters such as learning rate, number of neurons, activation functions and number of filters. Without proper optimization, networks can be affected by under- or over-fitting, leading to poor generalization over unseen data. Optimizing these parameters increases convergence speed and improves classification or regression accuracy. In applications, grid search or metaheuristics are used for hyperparameter optimization.

In this study, a classification application was performed using an publicly available thyroid disease dataset. In the context of the study, centralized learning, federated learning algorithms and client-based learning approaches were analyzed comparatively. CNN is preferred as the learning model, and hyperparameter optimization was implemented through the AOA metaheuristic. Furthermore, experimental parameters such as the number of clients and the number of rounds that affect the federated learning performance were analyzed.

2 RELATED WORKS

In the existing literature, it is seen that deep learning methods are effectively used in many healthcare applications such as disease diagnosis, clinical decision support systems, prediction of patient hospitalization time and so on. In a study, an application for the diagnosis of pneumonia using X-ray images was developed [7]. The results show that the ideal results are obtained by using a pre-trained DenseNet-169 architecture in combination with a support vector machine (SVM) classifier. In a study conducted in 2023, a heart disease diagnosis application was performed using CNN and LSTM methods [8]. An 89% accuracy rate was achieved with the proposed hybrid model. [9] developed a deep learning-based model for the diagnosis of stomach cancer. In the study, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was applied for dimensionality reduction, followed by a CNN-based classifier. According to the results, 95.9% accuracy was achieved in 'sample type' classification, while 50.5% accuracy was achieved in 'vital status' classification. In another study, a model based on ultrasound images and a CNN classifier was used to diagnose liver disease [10]. The performance of

the model was evaluated with a 10-fold cross-validation technique and an accuracy rate of over 90% was obtained.

Some researchers have used metaheuristic algorithms to improve the performance of the CNN model. [11] used a CNN architecture optimized with Ant Colony Optimization in their study for the diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease. As a result of the applied method, a classification accuracy of 98.67% was achieved. In another study, a model for COVID-19 diagnosis was developed with a ResNet-50 based CNN architecture using chest X-ray images [12]. Advanced Squirrel Search Optimization Algorithm is applied to improve the performance of the model. It is reported that the proposed hybrid model outperforms the CNN models optimized with Squirrel Search, Genetic Algorithm and Grey Wolf Optimization Algorithm. In a study conducted in 2023, a CNN model whose hyperparameters were optimized with AOA for breast mass classification was developed and an accuracy rate of 96% was achieved as a result of the method applied [13].

The federated learning framework is an innovative technology developed in the field of artificial intelligence and research in this field has been increasing in recent years. The federated learning approach is gaining more and more attention, especially in various problems of healthcare industry applications where data privacy concerns are at the forefront. [14] implemented an application on heart attack prediction within the scope of federated learning system. Logistic regression method was used as the local learning model and the model achieved successful results with an accuracy rate of 88%. In another study, prostate cancer diagnosis was performed using a federated learning approach based on magnetic resonance images [15]. According to the findings, a performance improvement of 9.5% to 14.8% was achieved with federated learning compared to client based learning models. [16] developed a federated learning algorithm called FedBrain for brain tumor diagnosis. According to the results, the proposed method reduces the communication overhead and achieves the highest average accuracy rate of 79% compared to similar approaches. In a different study, an application for the diagnosis of pulmonary diseases based on cough sounds was implemented [17]. In the study, federated learning approach was used and CNN architecture was applied as the local model. As a result, a successful classification performance was achieved with an accuracy rate of 98%.

Thyroid diseases are among the clinically important health problems, and various studies have been carried out with machine learning-based methods in the diagnosis of these diseases. A study in 2020 used the knowledge graph and long short term memory model for thyroid disease diagnosis and achieved 88.86% accuracy [18]. In another study, ResNET-50 deep learning architecture was used to predict recurrent thyroid cancer and an AUC of 0.9 was obtained [19]. In the existing literature, there is limited application of federated learning approach in the field of thyroid disease diagnosis. In a 2021 study, a federated learning system and CNN-based model architectures were used to classify thyroid disease using ultrasound data [20]. According to external validation results, AUROC values ranged between 75% and 86% in the federated learning approach, while these values were between 73% and 91% in traditional deep learning methods.

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Data Collection

In this study, federated learning algorithms are compared with centralized learning and client-based learning approaches for thyroid disease classification. The dataset used includes thyroid disease records from 1987 collected by the Garavan Institute and J. Ross Quinlan at the New South Wales Institute, Sydney, Australia. While 3078 records were used for training the model, 694 records were reserved as test data. A sample five records structure of the dataset is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Thyroid disease dataset

Features	Record1	Record2	Record3	Record4	Record5
age	41	70	18	59	80
sex	F	F	F	F	F
on thyroxine	f	f	t	f	f
query on thyroxine	f	f	f	f	f
on antithyroid medication	f	f	f	f	f
sick	f	f	f	f	f
pregnant	f	f	f	f	f
thyroid surgery	f	f	f	f	f
I131 treatment	f	f	f	f	f
query hypothyroid	f	f	f	f	f
query hyperthyroid	f	f	f	f	f
lithium	f	f	f	f	f
goitre	f	f	f	f	f
tumor	f	f	f	f	f
hypopituitary	f	f	f	f	f
psych	f	f	f	f	f
TSH measured	t	t	t	f	t
TSH	1.3	0.72	0.03	?	2.2
T3 measured	t	t	f	f	t
T3	2.5	1.2	?	?	0.6
TT4 measured	t	t	t	t	t
TT4	125	61	183	72	80
T4U measured	t	t	t	t	t
T4U	1.14	0.87	1.3	0.92	0.7
FTI measured	t	t	t	t	t
FTI	109	70	141	78	115
TBG measured	f	f	f	f	f
Class	negative	negative	negative	negative	sick

3.2 CNN Model

Convolutional Neural Network is a deep learning-based artificial neural network architecture that is particularly effective on image processing, video analysis and spatial data [21]. Since the first versions used by LeCun et al. [22], CNNs have been widely used in visual recognition, medical image analysis, autonomous driving, face recognition and many other artificial intelligence applications.

In this study, a Conv1D-based deep learning model for one-dimensional (1D) data is built. In the first layer of the model, local features are learned using a Conv1D layer with 41 filters and a kernel size of 3. Then, MaxPooling1D layer was applied to reduce the spatial dimension and reduce the number of parameters. The resulting feature map was converted into vectorial form with a Flatten layer and processed with a fully connected layer with 128 neurons and ReLU activation. In the last layer, binary classification is performed using an output layer with a sigmoid activation function. This structure provides an effective solution in terms of both accuracy and computational efficiency, especially for classification problems.

3.3 AOA Metaheuristic

The Archimedes Optimization Algorithm is a nature-inspired metaheuristic global optimization algorithm developed by [23]. Based on Archimedes' principle of buoyancy of liquids, AOA mathematically models the behavior of individuals (solutions) as they rise, float, equilibrate and move in a pool of solutions. This algorithm is specifically designed for solving complex, nonlinear, multidimensional and multimodal optimization problems and is notable for its balanced exploration and exploitation capabilities.

In this study, AOA is used for hyperparameter optimization of a CNN model. AOA is a metaheuristic algorithm based on the principles of physical equilibrium, where each candidate solution is

updated with volume, density and acceleration properties. The algorithm optimizes four parameters: number of filters (filters, between 16-64), number of neurons in the fully connected layer (dense_units, between 32-128), mini-batch size (batch_size, between 16-64) and learning rate (learning_rate, between 0.0001-0.01). The optimization process was carried out with a population of 5 individuals and over 5 iterations. The fitness of each individual was determined based on the accuracy values evaluated by 5-fold cross-validation. The best model parameters were obtained by updating the parameter combination with the best fitness value throughout the iterations. In this process, the position of each individual was optimized by an acceleration-based update mechanism.

3.4 FedAvg Algorithm

In 2017, [24] developed the Federated Averaging (FedAvg) algorithm, which stands out as one of the first model aggregation strategies in the federated learning literature. In this algorithm, each client updates model parameters on its local data and these parameters are transmitted to a central server. The server creates a common global model by taking a weighted average of all incoming local models. This newly created model is distributed to clients for the next round of training. The process is repeated for a set number of iterations to improve the performance of the model across the entire system.

3.5 FedProx Algorithm

Federated Proximal (FedProx) is an optimization algorithm used in federated learning to better manage data heterogeneity (non-IID distributions) [25]. FedProx, a generalization of the FedAvg algorithm, adds a proximal term to limit the distance to the global model when updating clients' local models. This approach is specifically designed to mitigate the detrimental effects of inter-device data distribution differences on the centralized model.

3.6 FedDyn Algorithm

Federated Dynamics (FedDyn) is a FL algorithm proposed to reduce the learning performance degradation due to data heterogeneity [26]. In traditional federated learning algorithms, clients are trained on their local data and the central model is updated by averaging. However, this approach can make it difficult for the model to converge on non-IID data. FedDyn, on the other hand, adds a dynamic regularization term to each client's local optimization, making the training of clients more consistent with the global model.

3.7 MOON Algorithm

Model-Contrastive Federated Learning (MOON) is a contrastive learning-based algorithm proposed to mitigate the mismatch problems caused by data heterogeneity in the FL environment [27]. Traditional methods (e.g. FedAvg, FedProx) struggle to directly align each client's model with the global model when there are different data distributions across clients. MOON aims to solve this problem with a contrastive loss function that aims to increase the similarity between model representations.

4 EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

This study compares centralized learning, client-based learning and federated learning algorithms for thyroid disease diagnosis. The dataset is randomly distributed to three clients. CNN was used as the learning model and hyperparameter optimization was achieved with the AOA algorithm. The comparison of the methods according to the performance measures is shown in Table 2.

In cases where class labels are unbalanced or heterogeneously distributed, it is more appropriate to consider macro-level performance measures in model evaluations. According to the results obtained, the centralized learning approach showed the highest success with an accuracy of 90.69%, while the FedProx algorithm performed quite close with a macro accuracy of 90.68%.

Figure 1 shows the confusion matrices of the methods used. It is observed that the prediction success for the “sick” class is low, especially in client-based learning approaches. However, with FedAvg and FedProx federated algorithms, the classification performance for this class was significantly improved due to the collaboration between the clients. The local learning model of client 3 was able to predict only 24 “sick” classes, while collaborative learning with the FedProx algorithm correctly classified 42 out of 50 “sick” instances. On the other hand, the performance levels obtained with FedDyn and MOON algorithms were found to be significantly lower.

Table 2: Performance comparisons of algorithms

Model	Algorithm	Macro Acc	Macro F1 score	Micro Acc	Micro F1 score
1DCNN-AOA	Centralized training	90.69	92.66	98.13	98.13
	Client1 training	74.30	78.46	95.10	95.10
	Client2 training	86.15	86.82	96.54	96.54
	Client3 training	73.53	78.78	95.39	95.39
	FedAvg	89.07	88.36	96.83	96.83
	FedDyn	67.77	74.02	94.96	94.96
	FedProx	90.68	87.55	96.40	96.40
	MOON	79.46	83.45	96.11	96.11

Figure 1: Confusion matrices

The results for the experimental settings are presented in Figure 2 and Figure 3. When the number of clients was increased to 10, the classification performance of FedProx and FedAvg

algorithms dropped below 80%. Also, FedDyn and MOON algorithms could not successfully predict the “sick” class when more than seven clients were used. Increasing the number of rounds from 5 to 10 did not result in a significant performance difference for FedAvg and FedProx algorithms, whereas for the MOON algorithm, the increase in the number of rounds resulted in a decrease in accuracy.

Figure 2: Impact of the number of clients

Figure 3: Impact of the number of rounds

5 CONCLUSION

Federated learning enables different healthcare institutions to develop joint artificial intelligence models while protecting data privacy in disease diagnosis. This approach facilitates inter-institutional collaboration, especially in cases where the sharing of patient data is restricted for legal

or ethical reasons. Models trained on broader and more diverse data sources enable more accurate and early diagnosis of diseases. This improves the quality of diagnostic processes and enhances overall success in healthcare.

In this study, federated learning algorithms were compared with centralized and client-based training approaches for the classification of thyroid disease. According to the results obtained, the FedProx algorithm achieved an accuracy rate close to that of centralized learning, while demonstrating a clear advantage over client-based training. In particular, when data distribution among clients was heterogeneous, the federated learning approach achieved higher classification performance.

The findings reveal that the application of horizontal and vertical federated learning approaches among healthcare institutions in a country has significant potential in terms of developing smart diagnostic systems and improving the overall quality of healthcare services. This enables more accurate diagnoses at the individual patient level and allows for the data-driven and effective shaping of healthcare policies at the national level.

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